

**m x m O'LCHAMLI KVADRAT MATRITSANING ASOSIY VA
YORDAMCHI DIOGNALLARIDA VA ULARDAN YUQORIDA
JOYLASHGAN BARCHA ELEMENTLARINI NOLGA ALMASHTIRISH**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada $m \times m$ o'lchamli kvadrat matritsaning asosiy va yordamchi dioganallarida va ulardan yuqorida joylashgan barcha elementlarini nolga tengladik. Ushbu jarayonni esa class tipidan foydalanib yoritdik. Dasturni C++ va Python dasturlash tilida yechimni olib ular ustida experiment o'tkazdik.

Kalit so'zlar: Matritsa, bir o'lchamli matritsa, ikki o'lchamli matritsa va class.

**ЗАМЕНИТЕ ВСЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ, РАСПОЛОЖЕННЫЕ НА ГЛАВНОЙ,
ВСПОМОГАТЕЛЬНЫХ ДИАГОНАЛЯХ И ВЫШЕ НИХ НА НУЛЬ
КВАДРАТНОЙ МАТРИЦЫ РАЗМЕРОВ $m \times m$**

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Аннотация: В этой статье мы устанавливаем все элементы квадратной матрицы $m \times m$ на главной и вспомогательной диагоналях и над ними равными нулю. Мы рассмотрели этот процесс, используя тип класса. Мы взяли решение программы на языках программирования C++ и Python и провели на них эксперимент.

Ключевые слова: Матрица, одномерная матрица, двумерная матрица и класс.

REPLACE ALL ELEMENTS LOCATED ON THE MAIN AND AUXILIARY DIAGONALS AND ABOVE THEM TO ZERO OF THE SQUARE MATRIX OF DIMENSIONS $m \times m$

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Annotation: In this article, we set all elements of the $m \times m$ square matrix on the main and auxiliary diagonals and above them to zero. We covered this process using the class type. We took the solution of the program in C++ and Python programming language and conducted an experiment on them.

Key words: Matrix, one-dimensional matrix, two-dimensional matrix and class.

Kirish

Massiv – bu bir xil toifali, chekli qiymatlarning tartiblangan to’plamidir.

Ikki o’lchamli statik massivlarning e’lon qilish:

Toifa massiv_nomi [massiv_satrlari_soni][massiv_ustunlari_soni];

Ikki o’lchamli static massivlarining⁵¹ e’lon qilinishida, bir o’lchamlidan farqi, massiv nomidan keyin qirrali qavs ichida ikkita qiymat yozilganligidadir. Bulardan birinchisi, satrlar soni, ikkinchisi esa ustunlar sonini bildiradi. Ya’ni ikki o’lchamli massiv elementiga ikkita indeks orqali murojaat qilinadi. Ikki o’lchamli massivlar matematika kursidan ma’lum bo’lgan matritsalar⁵²ni eslatadi.

Ikki o’lchamli statik massiv e’loniga misol:

Int a[3][3], b[2][4];

A matritsa			B matritsa			
a_{00}	a_{01}	a_{02}	b_{00}	b_{01}	b_{02}	b_{03}
a_{10}	a_{11}	a_{12}	b_{10}	b_{11}	b_{12}	b_{13}
a_{20}	a_{21}	a_{22}				

A matritsa 3 ta satr, 3 ta ustunga ega;

B matritsa 2 ta satr, 4 ta ustunga ega;

⁵¹ Qudrat Abdurahimov <http://dasturch.uz>

⁵² Otaxanov N. A. Programmalash bo’yicha laboratoriya ishlari. Namangan, 2001. 36 b

Ikki o`lchamli massivlarda 1-indeks satrini, 2-indeks ustunini bildiradi.

Birinchi satrning dastlabki elementi a_{10} - a biru nol element deb o`qiladi. a o`n deyilmaydi.

m ta satr va n ta ustunga ega bo`lgan massivga (mxn) o`lchamli massiv deyiladi. Agar $m=n$ (satrlari va ustunlar soni teng) bo`lsa kvadrat massiv deyiladi.

Masala: m x n o`lchamli kvadrat matritsa berilgan. Matritsaning asosiy va yordamchi diognallarida va ulardan yuqorida joylashgan barcha elementlarni nolga almashtiruvchi programma tuzildi.

Dastur kodi:

```
#include <iostream>
using namespace std;

class Matrix
{
private:
int size;
int **data;
public:
Matrix(int m)
{
size = m;
data = new int*[size];
for(int i = 0; i < size; i++)
{
data[i] = new int[size];
}
}
void setElement(int i, int j, int value)

{
data[i][j] = value;
}

void printMatrix() {
cout << "Matritsa:" << endl;
for(int i = 0; i < size; i++) {
for(int j = 0; j < size; j++) {
cout << data[i][j] << "\t";
```

```
}
cout << endl;
}
}

void setZeros() {
for(int i = 0; i < size; i++) {
data[i][i] = 0;
data[i][size - 1 - i] = 0;
}
}
};

int main() {
int m;
cout << "Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: ";
cin >> m;

Matrix matrix(m);

for(int i = 0; i < m; i++) {

for(int j = 0; j < m; j++) {
int value;
cout << "Matritsa[" << i << "][" << j << "] ni kiriting: ";
cin >> value;
matrix.setElement(i, j, value);
}
}

cout << endl;

matrix.printMatrix();

matrix.setZeros();

cout << endl;

matrix.printMatrix();
```

```
return 0;  
}
```

Kompyuter xotirasiga kiritish:

```
1  #include <iostream>  
2  using namespace std;  
3  
4  class Matrix {  
5  private:  
6      int size;  
7      int **data;  
8  public:  
9      Matrix(int m) {  
10         size = m;  
11         data = new int*[size];  
12         for(int i = 0; i < size; i++) {  
13             data[i] = new int[size];  
14         }  
15     }  
16  
17     void setElement(int i, int j, int value) {  
18         data[i][j] = value;  
19     }  
20  
21     void printMatrix() {  
22         cout << "Matritsa:" << endl;  
23         for(int i = 0; i < size; i++) {  
24             for(int j = 0; j < size; j++) {  
25                 cout << data[i][j] << "\t";  
26             }  
27             cout << endl;  
28         }  
29     }  
30 }
```

```
26     }  
27     cout << endl;  
28 }  
29 }  
30  
31 void setZeros() {  
32     for(int i = 0; i < size; i++) {  
33         data[i][i] = 0;  
34         data[i][size - 1 - i] = 0;  
35     }  
36 }  
37 };  
38  
39 int main() {  
40     int m;  
41     cout << "Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: ";  
42     cin >> m;  
43  
44     Matrix matrix(m);  
45  
46     for(int i = 0; i < m; i++) {  
47         for(int j = 0; j < m; j++) {  
48             int value;  
49             cout << "Matritsa[" << i << "][" << j << "] ni kiriting: ";  
50             cin >> value;  
51             matrix.setElement(i, j, value);  
52         }  
53     }  
54  
55     cout << endl;  
56 }
```

```

39 int main() {
40     int m;
41     cout << "Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: ";
42     cin >> m;
43
44     Matrix matrix(m);
45
46     for(int i = 0; i < m; i++) {
47         for(int j = 0; j < m; j++) {
48             int value;
49             cout << "Matritsa[" << i << "][" << j << "] ni kiriting: ";
50             cin >> value;
51             matrix.setElement(i, j, value);
52         }
53     }
54
55     cout << endl;
56
57     matrix.printMatrix();
58
59     matrix.setZeros();
60
61     cout << endl;
62
63     matrix.printMatrix();
64
65     return 0;
66 }

```

Natijasi:

```

Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: 5
Matritsa[0][0] ni kiriting: 7
Matritsa[0][1] ni kiriting: 8
Matritsa[0][2] ni kiriting: 9
Matritsa[0][3] ni kiriting: 4
Matritsa[0][4] ni kiriting: 6
Matritsa[1][0] ni kiriting: 5
Matritsa[1][1] ni kiriting: 15
Matritsa[1][2] ni kiriting: 12
Matritsa[1][3] ni kiriting: 14
Matritsa[1][4] ni kiriting: 16
Matritsa[2][0] ni kiriting: 98
Matritsa[2][1] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[2][2] ni kiriting: 56
Matritsa[2][3] ni kiriting: 35
Matritsa[2][4] ni kiriting: 65
Matritsa[3][0] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[3][1] ni kiriting: 95
Matritsa[3][2] ni kiriting: 45
Matritsa[3][3] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[3][4] ni kiriting: 65
Matritsa[4][0] ni kiriting: 46
Matritsa[4][1] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[4][2] ni kiriting: 98
Matritsa[4][3] ni kiriting: 45
Matritsa[4][4] ni kiriting: 65

```

```

Matritsa:
7      8      9      4      6
5      15     12     14     16
98     78     56     35     65
78     95     45     78     65
46     78     98     45     65

```

```

Matritsa:
0      8      9      4      0
5      0      12     0      16
98     78     0      35     65
78     0      45     0      65
0      78     98     45     0

```

Dasturni Python kodi:

```
class Matrix:
    def __init__(self, m):
        self.size = m
        self.data = [[0] * self.size for _ in range(self.size)]

    def setElement(self, i, j, value):
        self.data[i][j] = value

    def printMatrix(self):
        print("Matritsa:")
        for row in self.data:
            for element in row:
                print(element, end="\t")
            print()

    def setZeros(self):
        for i in range(self.size):
            self.data[i][i] = 0
            self.data[i][self.size - 1 - i] = 0

m = int(input("Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: "))

matrix = Matrix(m)

for i in range(m):
    for j in range(m):
        value = int(input(f"Matritsa[{i}][{j}] ni kiriting: "))
        matrix.setElement(i, j, value)

print()
matrix.printMatrix()

matrix.setZeros()

print()
matrix.printMatrix()
Kompyuter xotirasiga kiritish:
```

```

class Matrix:
    def __init__(self, m):
        self.size = m
        self.data = [[0] * self.size for _ in range(self.size)]

    def setElement(self, i, j, value):
        self.data[i][j] = value

    def printMatrix(self):
        print("Matritsa:")
        for row in self.data:
            for element in row:
                print(element, end="\t")
            print()

    def setZeros(self):
        for i in range(self.size):
            self.data[i][i] = 0
            self.data[i][self.size - 1 - i] = 0

m = int(input("Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: "))

matrix = Matrix(m)

```

```

        for i in range(self.size):
            self.data[i][i] = 0
            self.data[i][self.size - 1 - i] = 0

m = int(input("Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: "))

matrix = Matrix(m)

for i in range(m):
    for j in range(m):
        value = int(input(f"Matritsa[{i}][{j}] ni kiriting: "))
        matrix.setElement(i, j, value)

print()
matrix.printMatrix()

matrix.setZeros()

print()
matrix.printMatrix()

```

Natijasi:

```

Matritsaning o'lchamini kiriting: 5
Matritsa[0][0] ni kiriting: 7
Matritsa[0][1] ni kiriting: 8
Matritsa[0][2] ni kiriting: 9
Matritsa[0][3] ni kiriting: 4
Matritsa[0][4] ni kiriting: 6
Matritsa[1][0] ni kiriting: 5
Matritsa[1][1] ni kiriting: 15
Matritsa[1][2] ni kiriting: 12
Matritsa[1][3] ni kiriting: 14
Matritsa[1][4] ni kiriting: 16
Matritsa[2][0] ni kiriting: 98
Matritsa[2][1] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[2][2] ni kiriting: 56
Matritsa[2][3] ni kiriting: 35
Matritsa[2][4] ni kiriting: 65
Matritsa[3][0] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[3][1] ni kiriting: 95
Matritsa[3][2] ni kiriting: 45
Matritsa[3][3] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[3][4] ni kiriting: 65
Matritsa[4][0] ni kiriting: 46

Matritsa[4][0] ni kiriting: 46
Matritsa[4][1] ni kiriting: 78
Matritsa[4][2] ni kiriting: 98
Matritsa[4][3] ni kiriting: 45
Matritsa[4][4] ni kiriting: 65

Matritsa:
7 8 9 4 6
5 15 12 14 16
98 78 56 35 65
78 95 45 78 65
46 78 98 45 65

Matritsa:
0 8 9 4 0
5 0 12 0 16
98 78 0 35 65
78 0 45 0 65
0 78 98 45 0
    
```

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. <http://dasturchi.uz>
2. Informatika va programmalsh.O'quv qo'llanma. Mualliflar: A.A.Xaldjigitov, Sh.F.Madraximov, U.E.Adamboev, O'zMU, 2005 yil, 145 bet.
3. Otaxanov N. A. Programmalash bo'yicha laboratoriya ishlari. Namangan, 2001. 36 b
4. Otaxanov N. A. Programmalash bo'yicha masalalar to'plami. Namangan, 2000 y. 36 b
5. Otaxanov N. A. TURBO PASKAL dasturlash tili. Namangan, 2002 y. 96 b
6. Qudrat Abdurahimov <http://dasturch.uz>
7. www.Intuit.ru. Интернет-Университет информационных технологий. Москва.
8. Ш.Ф. Мадрахимов, С. М. Гайназаров С++ тилида программалаш асослари. Т. 2009